

Smart Materials In Orthodontics : A Futuristic Approach

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Introduction

The importance of a well-coordinated interaction of orthodontists with biomedical engineers for the production of many customised orthodontic appliances has been underappreciated¹. Usually, the bio-medical engineers, hired by many orthodontic appliance manufacturing companies, develop the appliances, overlooking the day-to-day clinical difficulties faced by the orthodontists in their busy practices². Innovations are the need of the hour which could address a critical clinical concern; for example, a material that has easy handling characteristics and shortens chair side time or one that significantly improves the quality of treatment by addressing important variables such as treatment, duration and cost. The aim of this review is to describe the current trends and innovations of biomedical materials and their implications in orthodontic science^{3,4}.

Shape-memory polymers (SMPs):

Polymers play a vital role in orthodontics and dentistry due to their diverse applications. Aesthetic concerns, particularly the metallic appearance of traditional orthodontic appliances like brackets and archwires, have driven the development of alternatives such as ceramic, plastic, or polycarbonate brackets and Teflon-coated archwires⁵. Shape Memory Polymers (SMPs) are advanced materials that can return to their original shape after deformation when triggered by external stimuli like heat, light, or water. Their unique properties include transparency, lightweight nature, cost-effectiveness, and a shape-recovery force lasting up to three months⁶. With a glass transition temperature close to body temperature, SMPs are especially useful for aligning and leveling teeth in patients seeking aesthetic solutions. These polymers are effective in correcting malaligned or severely rotated teeth and have become increasingly popular among

clinicians^{7,8}.

Brackets with force moment sensors :

When a two couple system or an indeterminate force system is employed using orthodontic appliances, the amount of forces and moments cannot be appropriately determined. Lapatki et al. developed a smart bracket equipped with a stress sensor system embedded in its base, designed to measure the three-dimensional forces and moments acting on the bracket and subsequently on the tooth. None of the material has been tested yet , research is still pending in this sector⁸⁻¹⁰.

Fig 1 : Brackets with force moment sensors

Self-healing materials : In recent decades, hydrogels with remarkable bio-mimicking characteristics have been developed. Studies have highlighted cross-linked hydrogels capable of self-healing, showcasing their advanced functional properties. These materials can be incorporated in wires and brackets in form of nano sized bubbles . When a bracket breaks, these bubbles release the monomer, which polymerizes upon exposure to air, filling the fractured space. This process helps reduce bracket and wire damage and shortens overall treatment time¹⁰⁻¹².

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Fig 2 : Hydrogel In Medicines

Biomimetic adhesives : Attaching brackets to the tooth surface involves preconditioning the enamel, which results in changes to its thickness and color. Hence to prevent damage to tooth surface a biomimetic material named Geckel was introduced. This adhesive combines elements inspired by the natural adhesion mechanisms of geckos and mussels, functioning effectively in both dry and wet environments. In orthodontics, biomimetic adhesives are applied by coating bracket bases with L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (DOPA), a key adhesive protein found in mussels. DOPA ensures strong bonding to the enamel surface. Works well in both dry and wet conditions¹³.

Fig 3: Showing gecko adhesive system

Self-cleaning materials : Plaque buildup around brackets and tooth surfaces can severely harm the periodontium, leading to issues like gingivitis, bone loss, and white spot lesions. The use of materials capable of effectively removing organic and inorganic deposits from calcified surfaces and brackets has been under research to mitigate these effects. The photocatalytic properties of titanium oxide with UV light are a key focus in orthodontic materials. Nickel-titanium archwires are modified into crystalline rutile by electrolytic titanium oxide film treatment followed by heat application¹⁴.

Biodegradable or bioresorbable miniimplants : These polymer materials address the risk of inflammation, infection, and loosening associated with conventional temporary anchorage devices. However, ensuring the safe removal of their byproducts from the body remains essential. By changing the ratio of PLA/PGA such product can be made. They have a setback of delayed resorption time. Continued studies and research will perhaps facilitate development of such a product¹².

Fluoride releasing materials : Bonding materials like compomers and resin-modified glass ionomer cements (RMGICs) have demonstrated a reduction in caries development but require further trials due to concerns about their bond strength. The transformation of hydroxyapatite into fluorapatite

enhances fluoride's anti-cariogenic properties, as high fluoride levels in plaque are bactericidal and help prevent enamel demineralization. Casein Phosphopeptide-Amorphous Calcium Phosphate (CPP-ACP) supports calcium and phosphate retention in plaque, preventing their loss and promoting remineralization¹⁵.

To maintain elevated fluoride levels in orthodontic patients, methods such as slow-release devices, chewing gums, and elastomers have been utilized, showing increased fluoride presence in the oral cavity. However, incorporating fluoride into these materials significantly alters their mechanical properties. Extensive trials are needed to establish standardized guidelines for fluoride use in orthodontics to minimize adverse effects like white spot lesions and ensure safe, effective treatment¹⁶.

BPA free polymers : Orthodontic materials must be biocompatible with oral tissues, non-toxic, and mechanically stable throughout treatment. A growing concern is the release of Bisphenol-A (BPA) from materials like polycarbonate brackets and orthodontic composites (e.g., bis-DMA), thermoformed Biocryl retainers and Transbond XT. BPA exposure is linked to health risks such as premature puberty, ovarian cancer, disruption of male reproductive organ development, and increased anxiety, depression, and social difficulties in children. Methods to reduce BPA leaching include soaking retainers in hot water for a few hours prior to delivery, removing any excess adhesive before curing, ensuring that all adhesive is fully cured around the bracket's peripheral margins, having the patient rinse with warm water after bonding, and/or using an orthodontic adhesive that does not contain a BPA derivative which includes EXA, EXB, Phenyl carbamoyloxy-propane dimethacrylate (PCDMA) and Aromatic-free urethane dimethacrylate monomers¹⁷.

Conclusion : This review explored biomedical materials, their current trends, orthodontic applications, and future perspectives. Collaboration between orthodontists and biomedical engineers is crucial for customizing orthodontic appliances, ensuring better patient outcomes with minimal complications from the tools used.

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